

Exploration of artificial intelligence's and its impact on today's youth

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Annotation. Digital technologies have become actively used by people in their daily lives and are constantly being improved. Public opinion regarding the rapid introduction of digital tools into human life has a polar significance: for some, digitalization is beneficial, for others it poses a threat. The field of education, as one of the key areas influencing the formation and formation of the personality of future specialists, is subject to constant transformations. The introduction of artificial intelligence into the educational process is the most discussed topic of recent times. A new resonance in this area was caused by the use of neural networks by students in the preparation of certification works. In this regard, the academic community and "public figures" began to discuss the application of prohibitions and restrictions in this area. In this regard, it is important to understand how the younger generation treats the use of neural networks in education.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, education, youth, educational process.

Artificial intelligence systems are already contributing to the field of education, allowing for a more personalized approach to teaching and learning. In addition, artificial intelligence-based technologies have begun to change the landscape of health and well-being, especially in the field of mental health. While the activities discussed in this Part II are revolutionary because they can promote engagement, learning and well-being on a larger scale than previously possible, it is important to emphasize the fact that, like many artificial intelligence systems, these technologies are designed in such a way that they can limit the full participation of young people from unrepresented strata of the population. Education with AI technology in the classroom - such as intelligent tutoring systems, AI-based curricula and intelligent virtual reality - can improve learning outcomes and provide an exciting learning experience for young people. AI-based curriculum plans, often referred to as "curriculum playlists", and intelligent tutoring systems offer personalized learning experiences for young people by adapting learning and feedback to student opportunities and needs - the first through daily individual learning sessions based on the curriculum that the system compiles for each student, and the second through individual tutoring, the purpose of which is to simulate human tutoring. Intelligent learning systems can also be incorporated into other forms of educational technologies, such as virtual reality

systems. For example, a character in the process of immersion in virtual reality can offer AI-guided recommendations and support, helping the user interact with the virtual world in a way that facilitates learning. Over time, as lower costs and increased Internet connectivity allow more schools and homes to access AI-based technologies, the future of AI in education opens up opportunities for personalized learning nationwide.

Learning tools for educators - especially in low-resource communities - with the skills and support to intelligently integrate AI-based technologies into the learning process. The level of teacher training and the manifestation of effectiveness in the means of education, based on the use of AI technologies. Ways to involve teachers and students in the process of developing educational technologies using AI. To implement personalized, interest-based learning at scale, while taking into account the diversity of paths and hobbies of students from different demographic groups, cultures and social contexts. Using AI-based personalization at scale to expand access to education in regions of the world where education is difficult for the general population, including young people. Providing meaningful tools for the youth who use them. Here, it is necessary to balance the need of AI systems for data and ensure the confidentiality and security of confidential student data at both the individual and group levels. To ensure that both AI technologies themselves and the decision makers who control and engage AI will approach the acquisition, storage, transmission and analysis of AI-based student data ethically correctly and identify functions that should not be performed for privacy, security or ethical reasons.

Educational institutions can automate basic administrative processes, and in the case of important or complex decisions, they can use algorithms to obtain information for human decision-making. For example, schools can use machine learning and artificial intelligence-based technologies to sort student academic performance data. AI education, both in formal and non-formal educational institutions, needs to be made accessible and fun for young people - starting with understanding data/computing speed. Studying and working with data is central to understanding the role of big data in AI machine learning systems and the main challenges associated with these systems. There are currently many frameworks around the concept of digital citizenship regarding online privacy and security that have helped drive the reform. As AI-based technologies change our understanding of privacy and security issues in our digital world, how can we involve a variety of stakeholders, including policy makers, educators, parents and educators, as well as young people themselves, in developing educational frameworks that take into

account the interaction between AI systems and security and privacy on the Internet¹.

For example, laws and regulations governing the confidentiality of digital data of young people tend to assign all or most of the authority to consent to data collection with parents or guardians, and not with the young people themselves. In some circumstances (particularly in the field of education), consent to the exchange of youth data may be given by another adult party (school) as a substitute for parental or guardian consent. Thus, with technology, young people find themselves without any legal rights under federal law to consent or disagree with their personal data being collected or used by the AI system. In these cases, where concerns may arise about the impact of privacy and security on young people, stakeholders may need to act through channels and young people themselves can make a meaningful contribution to this activity.

Today's youth – more popularly known as the Gen Z and Generation Alpha – have grown up with technology. Chances are, they have no idea what a beeper or a typewriter is. They are surrounded by AI even though they may not know what it is. Adults use different gadgets and devices for managing their daily schedules and responsibilities. It is thus not surprising that the youth also know – or expect to know – how to use these devices. The widespread use of smartphones, tablets, and personal computers has helped kids and teens to familiarise themselves with technology, and more specifically with AI.

The most common type of artificial intelligence present today is what experts call weak AI. This is the AI found in algorithms used to predict responses. The best example of these algorithms is found in social media websites that recommend ads or videos specific to the user's interests.

The introduction of digital technologies and tools in various fields is very fast, automating or eliminating routine functions altogether, but it is very difficult to predict the consequences of such changes in the long term. The field of education is one of the most important areas within which the formation of a personality's worldview, the development of creativity, critical thinking, etc. takes place. In the field of vocational education, the formation of a future specialist is taking place, and the replacement of traditional training functions can lead to the emergence of specialists who have "grown up" in digital reality, which can greatly affect the results of their work. Automation, the use of robotics, the introduction of neural networks in various professional fields and other innovations can affect the socialization of a person, lead to the loss of creative and social skills necessary in

¹ Мухамадиева, К. Б. Анализ исследований по применению искусственного интеллекта в высшем образовании / К. Б. Мухамадиева // Образование и проблемы развития общества. – 2020. – № 2(11). – С. 119-124

both personal and professional spheres. Such a situation in the future may provoke a transformation of the entire educational paradigm, where there will be a rejection of the traditional educational process and the emergence of innovative teaching methods and technologies.

Artificial intelligence has many uses. Since it is human-made, AI can be used for advantages or disadvantages intentions. As AI is highly adaptable to any setting, the young generation can enjoy it for educational and entertainment purposes. It should be noted that adults can easily become susceptible to the harmful use of their data. Monitoring their usage and educating them on the proper ways to use AI is the best way to prevent any negative impacts of the technology.

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